

THE GAME CHANGER: THIRD-PARTY FUNDING IN CROSS-BORDER LITIGATION

1. Introduction

Third-party (litigation) funding - TPF or TPLF - is a financial arrangement where an entity that is not directly involved in a legal dispute (third party) provides funding to one of the parties involved in litigation or arbitration, with the understanding that they will receive a portion of any recovered sums should the case succeed, and nothing if it fails.¹ Currently, TPF is more prominent in commercial and investment arbitration, but its importance is noticeably rising in civil litigation, particularly in collective redress.² Historically, this type of funding by entities uninvolved in the dispute was labelled as maintenance or champers and deemed unlawful in common law countries.³ TPF has typically been viewed with scepticism in Europe, especially in comparison to its more common use in common law jurisdictions like Australia,⁴ the USA, and the United Kingdom.⁵ In civil law countries, the costs of litigation are generally lower and punitive damages are not permit-

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¹ Also referred to as (alternative) litigation funding, litigation investment, third-party financing or legal finance.

² Kramer X. and Tillema I., "The Funding of Collective Redress by Entrepreneurial Parties: the EU and Dutch Context", *Revista Ítalo-Española de Derecho Procesal*, Procesos colectivos, Vol. 2, 165-181, Madrid 2021.

³ Jackson R., "Review of Civil Litigation Costs: Preliminary Report", The Stationery Office, 2009, p. 160. Available at <https://www.judiciary.uk/wp-content/uploads/JCO/Documents/Guidance/jackson-vol1-low.pdf>

⁴ Legg, M., *The Rise and Regulation of Litigation Funding in Australian Class Actions*, 2021 (4), pp. 221-234.

⁵ Lewis, J., *Third-Party Litigation Funding: A Boon or Bane to the Progress of Civil Justice?*, *The Georgetown Journal of Legal Ethics*, 2020, pp. 687-701.

ted, which may explain the lesser prevalence of TPF so far. Contemporary trends show restrictions against such funding arrangements relaxed or eliminated in some important jurisdictions,⁶ while others ignore or prohibit such practices in civil litigation, through legislations or jurisprudence.⁷

The significance of TPF in international arbitration - and to a lesser degree, civil litigation⁸ - has undeniably increased over the last decade across various sectors and procedural frameworks.⁹ However, both the concept of TPF and the procedural and regulatory developments accompanying it remain controversial.¹⁰ TPF in arbitration has long been the subject of polarized opinions. At one extreme, it's seen as highly detrimental, akin to an "arbitration antichrist," and on the other, it's hailed as exceptionally beneficial, "the best thing since sliced bread".¹¹ This range of opinions underscores the contentious nature of TPF within the arbitration community, reflecting deep divisions over its impact and utility.

Despite such divisive views on TPF, public debates have largely progressed from questioning the permissibility of TPF to discussing how to tackle specific concerns it raises. Under the absence of regulatory oversight, TPF expanded and evolved to a point where its use became too significant to ignore.¹² In 2021, the global litigation funding investment market was esti-

⁶In arbitration - Hong Kong and Singapore. International Council for Commercial Arbitration, "Report of the ICCA – Queen Mary Task Force on Third-Party Funding in International Arbitration", The ICCA Reports no. 4, [Electronic version], 2018, Retrieved January 7, 2024, from https://cdn.arbitration-icca.org/s3fs-public/document/media_document/Third-Party-Funding-Report%20.pdf, p. 5. (ICCA-Queen Mary Report).

⁷Hodges, C., Vogenauer, S., Tulibacka, M., *Costs and Funding of Civil Litigation: A Comparative Study*, COSTS AND FUNDING OF CIVIL LITIGATION, (ed. Hodges, C., Vogenauer, S., Tulibacka, M.), Oxford Legal Studies Research Paper No. 55-2009, [Electronic version], 2009, Retrieved December 13, 2023, from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1511714>

⁸For the different judicial treatment of TPF in arbitration and civil litigation, see: Lin, Y., *Third Party Funding in Litigation and Arbitration: A Dichotomy in China's Practice*, Kluwer Arbitration Blog, [Electronic version], 2023, Retrieved February 3, 2024, from <https://arbitrationblog.kluwerarbitration.com/2023/04/24/third-party-funding-in-litigation-and-arbitration-a-dichotomy-in-chinas-practice/>

⁹Haeri, H., HuelmoBaro, C., Gasparotti G., *Third-Party Funding in International Arbitration in The M&A Arbitration Guide*, Global Arbitration Review, [Electronic version], 2022, Retrieved January 3, 2024, from <https://globalarbitrationreview.com/guide/the-guide-ma-arbitration/4th-edition/article/third-party-funding-in-international-arbitration>

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹Perry, S., *Third-Party Funding: The Best Thing Since Sliced Bread?*, Global Arbitration Review, [Electronic version], 2012, Retrieved January 3, 2024, from <https://globalarbitrationreview.com/article/third-party-funding-the-best-thing-sliced-bread>

¹²The number of litigation funders in EU is hard to determine, with at least 45 such

mated at USD 12.2 billion and projected to reach approximately USD 25.8 billion by 2030 with a compound annual growth rate of roughly 9% between 2022 and 2030.¹³

Defining TPF has been contentious, challenging groups and institutions like the ICCA-Queen Mary Task Force¹⁴, UNCITRAL Working Group III¹⁵ and European Commission and Parliament.¹⁶ TPF evolved from historically dubious practices to a recognized means of enabling access to justice for those unable to afford litigation costs. It spans various forms, including commercial funding agreements and portfolio financing, beyond traditional legal support like contingency fees or specific types of insurance. This flexibility in application underscores TPF's role in diversifying legal finance, offering claimants and legal professionals novel mechanisms for pursuing legal actions, particularly in cases related to environment, health and safety and human rights.¹⁷

fundors known to operate in the Union. European Parliament resolution of 13 September 2022 with recommendations to the Commission on Responsible private funding of litigation (2020/2130(INL)). [Electronic version], 2020, Retrieved November 20, 2023, from https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2022-0308_EN.html#def_1_6, p. J.

¹³ Custom Market Insights: Global Litigation Funding Investment Market 2024-2033. [Electronic version], 2024, Retrieved March 21, 2024, from <https://www.custommarketinsights.com/report/litigation-funding-investment-market/For EU>, see: Saulnier, J., Koronthalyova, I., Müller, K., European Added Value Unit, Directorate-General for European Parliamentary Research Services (EPRS), *Responsible private funding of litigation*, [Electronic version], 2021, Retrieved November 25, 2023, from [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/662612/EPRS_STU\(2021\)662612_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/662612/EPRS_STU(2021)662612_EN.pdf)

¹⁴ The ICCA – Queen Mary Task Force Report.

¹⁵ See United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL), Working Group III (Investor-State Dispute Settlement Reform), Forty-third session (Vienna, 5–16 September 2022), 'Possible reform of investor-State dispute settlement (ISDS), Draft provisions on procedural reform', Note by the Secretariat, 11 July 2022 (A/CN.9/WG.III/WP.219), draft provision E-1, [Electronic version], 2022, Retrieved January 16, 2024, from https://uncitral.un.org/sites/uncitral.un.org/files/media-documents/uncitral/en/wp_219_-_draft_provisions_on_procedural_reform_.pdf

¹⁶ Recommendations as to the content of the proposal requested: Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on the regulation of third-party litigation funding. [Electronic version], 2021, Retrieved November 24, 2023, from https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/JURI-PR-680934_EN.pdf

¹⁷ Cordina, A., Storskrubb, E., *The Future of Regulation of Third-Party Litigation Funding in Europe*, Conference Report, Erasmus University Rotterdam. [Electronic version], 2022, Retrieved December 16, 2023, from https://www.bjutijdschriften.nl/tijdschrift/tijdschriftmediation/2022/2/TMD_1386-3878_2023_026_002_005

2. Understanding Third-Party Funding

2.1. The Role of Third-Party Funding in Access to Justice

Access to justice is increasingly hindered by high litigation costs¹⁸ „complex and lengthy procedures, decreasing public legal aid, and stringent conditions for cost exemptions, highlighting the growing necessity for external financing sources. Technological advancements and changes in the judicial system and society introduce both new challenges and opportunities.¹⁹ Two conceptual trends are noticeable in that regard.²⁰ One is the emergence of private forms of financing litigation costs in light of the gradual decline of state legal aid systems in civil matters.²¹ The second trend is policymakers’ attempts to reform the rules on litigation costs to make them more predictable, transparent, and proportional. This includes various forms of legal expenses insurance, fixed recoverable costs, cost-shifting rules, increased use of costs as court sanctions²² and even establishing the so-called litigation budget.²³

Against this backdrop, there’s a noticeable shift in litigation funding within Europe, moving from predominantly public to private sources. This shift is not merely a change in the source of funding; it heralds the rise of private entities and innovative business models, which introduce new approaches to overcoming the longstanding issue of financial obstacles to justice access. Within this evolving framework, TPF manifests in various forms. It encompasses a variety of arrangements other than ‘archetypal’ TPF provided by commercial funders²⁴, such as covering work carried out by legal counsel on a conditional fee or contingency basis and certain forms of

¹⁸ Sahani, V. S., *Rethinking the Impact of Third-Party Funding on Access to Civil Justice*, DePaul Law Review, DePaul University, 69, 2020, pp. 612-622.

¹⁹ Biard, A., Hoevenaars, J., Kramer X., Themeli, E., *Introduction: The Future of Access to Justice – Beyond Science Fiction*, New Pathways to Civil Justice in Europe (eds. A. Biard, J. Hoevenaars, X. Kramer, E. Themeli), Springer, [Electronic version], 2021, Retrieved November 21, 2023, from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-66637-8_1

²⁰ Ahmed, M., Kramer, X., *Global Developments and Challenges in Costs and Funding of Civil Justice*, Erasmus Law Review, no. 4, Rotterdam, 2021, p. 181.

²¹ This group includes various models of private financing of costs, such as legal expenses insurance, third-party funding, contingency fee agreements, and damages-based agreements.

²² Ahmed, M., Kramer, X., *op.cit.*, p. 181.

²³ Tidmarsch, J., *The Litigation Budget*, Vanderbilt Law Review, 68(3), 2015, pp. 855-918.

²⁴ Article 3(a) of the *Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on the regulation of third-party litigation funding*.

insurance – for both claimants and respondents.²⁵ TPF differs from contingency-fee arrangements and liability-insurance financing mainly in terms of the supporter’s identity; unlike a liability insurer or the plaintiff’s own counsel, the financier in TPF is a specialized entity created specifically to invest in lawsuits.²⁶ However, in a narrower sense, TPF often pertains to ‘non-recourse’ legal finance provided by a commercial funder under the terms of a funding agreement, typically to a claimant (or sometimes defendant) in return for a share of the amounts recovered in the proceeding. A more elaborate arrangement is ‘portfolio financing’,²⁷ whereby financing is provided in respect of a group or portfolio of claims held by a certain entity or entities, or to legal counsel working on multiple cases, usually on a conditional fee or contingency basis.²⁸

Although TPF is beneficial, in that it promotes access to justice for certain litigants, selection process of potential cases for funding shows clear limitations.²⁹ TPF is not usually feasible where non-monetary relief, such as an injunction or declaration, is the main remedy sought. TPF is most readily obtained for high value cases with good prospects of success.³⁰ The success rate is an obvious way of testing the funder’s selection process. This is often a matter of commercial confidence.³¹ Commercial litigation, small business disputes, patent/IP cases, and construction disputes are less attractive to funders due to high costs, complex nature, or technical challenges, although exceptions exist, particularly in group actions and quick-resolution adjudications.³²

The use of TPF generally does not impose additional financial burdens upon opposing parties.³³ However, where litigation funders have supported

²⁵ The ICCA-Queen Mary Report, p. 51.

²⁶ Wendel, W. B., *Paying the Piper But Not Calling the Tune: Litigation Financing and Professional Independence*, Akron Law Review, 52 (1), p. 8. [Electronic version], 2019, Retrieved January 27, 2024, from <https://ideaexchange.uakron.edu/akronlawreview/vol52/iss1/1>

²⁷ Portfolio financing is gaining in frequency in USA. Baker, T., ALI-ELI Webinar on Third Party Funding of Litigation, April 15th 2024 (online).

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ Jackson, R., *Review of Civil Litigation Costs: Final Report*, The Stationery Office, 2009, fn 96 p. 117. [Electronic version], 2009, Retrieved January 26, 2023, from <https://www.judiciary.uk/wp-content/uploads/JCO/Documents/Reports/jackson-final-report-140110.pdf>

³⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 118.

³¹ *Ibid.*

³² Jackson, R., “Review of Civil Litigation Costs: Preliminary Report”, The Stationery Office, 2009, pp. 161-163.

³³ Jackson, R., *Review of Civil Litigation Costs: Final Report*, p. 117.

or funded proceedings which are not successful, they should be jointly liable with claimants for any adverse costs they caused defendants to incur. Courts or administrative authorities should be granted adequate powers to ensure the effectiveness of such an obligation, and TPF agreements should not exclude responsibility for such adverse costs.³⁴ Does this go another way around – can funded party, provided it won the case, be granted the “reasonable costs” including the costs of litigation funder? The principle of ‘costs shifting’ is prevalent in arbitration in numerous jurisdictions and in general, the fact that a prevailing party has been funded has not been deemed relevant as a basis to deny the recovery of costs.³⁵

Funders are not always driven solely by economic interests and profits. Occasionally, funders may aim to provide financial support to a party in a proceeding for political, ideological, or even personal reasons. A distinction is proposed between these two forms of litigation financing.³⁶ The first type is called disinterested or commercial litigation funding, where funders act as passive investors, not directly involved in the merits of the case, except to the extent and in the manner permitted by law and the financial litigation agreement. The second type is interested litigation finance, where the primary motive of the funders is not profit, but rather achieving a specific goal through the process.³⁷ These goals can be positive, aimed at fostering

³⁴ *Preamble the Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on the regulation of third-party litigation funding*, para. 30

³⁵ In cases where the respondent has engaged in improper conduct, funded claimants might not only recoup arbitration costs but also the premium or success fee paid to their funders. This was exemplified in the *Essar Oilfield Services Ltd v Norscot Rig Management Pvt Ltd* case of 2016, where the English High Court upheld an ICC arbitration decision in London. The court confirmed the claimant could recover both legal costs and the success fee from the funder due to the respondent’s actions that necessitated funding. This precedent was further supported by the High Court in the 2021 case of *TenkeFungurume Mining SA v Katanga Contracting Services SAS*, where costs related to litigation funding agreements—including fixed and variable fees contingent on successful outcomes, plus compound interest—were awarded. These cases highlight the court’s willingness to allow recovery of comprehensive costs related to litigation funding when the respondent’s conduct justifies such measures. <https://woodsford.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/LexGTDT-Litigation-Funding-2023-Full-book.pdf>

³⁶ Wendel, W. Bradley (2019) “Paying the Piper But Not Calling the Tune: Litigation Financing and Professional Independence”. Jeremy Kidd, *To Fund or Not to Fund: The Need for Second-Best Solutions to the Litigation Finance Dilemma*, 8 J.L. ECON. & POL’Y 613 (2012); Maya Steinitz, *Whose Claim Is This Anyway? Third-Party Litigation Funding*, 95 MINN. L. REV. 1268 (2011).

³⁷ In a case where Philip Morris challenged Uruguay’s tobacco-control measures as expropriatory under a bilateral investment treaty, an arbitration panel upheld the regulations,

broader societal change, but the line between socially engaged financial support and vindictive or harassing actions is blurred and unclear.

2.2. Regulatory and Ethical Considerations

TPF is gaining popularity as it allows litigants to pursue claims without facing prohibitive costs, contributing to greater access to justice.³⁸ However, this trend has attracted scrutiny based on ethical concerns such as commodification of justice,³⁹ frivolous litigation, conflicts of interest between funder, funded party and lawyer of the funded party, and fee-splitting, especially in Europe, where regulatory landscape for litigation funding generally remains complex and unclear.⁴⁰

The first concern is commodification of justice.⁴¹ The majority of litigation financing is driven by profit. Critics of TPF who argue against the commodification of justice as immoral often overlook that the economic self-interest present in TPF can be compared to other accepted practices like insurance, contingency legal fees, venture capital, and bank loans, which similarly commodify aspects of risk and potential future gains.⁴² These practices are widely accepted despite their commodification aspects because they provide critical services that manage risk, facilitate access to services, and drive economic growth, all within regulated frameworks that safeguard against abuse. This context helps mitigate concerns about the commodifica-

recognizing them as a legitimate exercise of state power—illustrating a scenario where interested litigation finance might support broader societal goals. Harv. L. Rev., *International Arbitration - Investor-State Dispute Settlement - Tribunal Holds That Uruguay's Anti-Tobacco Regulations Do Not Violate Philip Morris's Investment Rights*, 130 HARV. L. REV. 1986 (2017). <https://harvardlawreview.org/print/vol-130/philip-morris-brands-sarl-v-oriental-republic-of-uruguay/>

³⁸ C. Hodges, S. Vogenauer & M. Tulibacka, *The Costs and Funding of Civil Litigation: A Comparative Perspective* (2010). Lewis J., *Third-Party Litigation Funding: A Boon or Bane to the Progress of Civil Justice?*, *The Georgetown Journal of Legal Ethics*, 2020, Vol. 33, p. 688.

³⁹ Radončić, Dž., *Third-Party Litigation Funding: Access to Justice or Commodification of Justice*, *Proceedings of the Kopaonik School of Natural Law – Slobodan Perović*, Belgrade, 2023, tom III, pp. 333-349.

⁴⁰ Cordina A., *op.cit.*

⁴¹ W. B. Wendel, *Alternative Litigation Finance and anti-Commodification Norms*, 63 *DePaul L. Rev.* 655 (2014), p. 657. Available at: <https://via.library.depaul.edu/law-review/vol63/iss2/16/>; Cordina A., *op.cit.*, p. 274-275.

⁴² Similarly, see: W. B. Wendel, *Alternative Litigation Finance and anti-Commodification Norms*, 63 *De Paul L. Rev.* 655 (2014). W. Bradley Wendel and Joshua P. Davis, *Complex Litigation Funding: Ethical Problem or Ethical Solution?*, 74 *HASTINGS L.J.* 1459 (2023). Available at: https://repository.uclawsf.edu/hastings_law_journal/vol74/iss5/8/

tion of justice in TPF, suggesting that, with proper regulation, it can similarly become a beneficial and accepted practice.⁴³

The second major criticism of TPF focuses on potential conflicts of interest between the funder, the claimant, and the lawyer. These conflicts may arise from pre-existing relationships, the funder's economic interests, their control over procedural decisions, and frivolous litigation.⁴⁴ Notably, funders might be motivated by profit to the extent that they could influence the management of the case or opt only for high-value cases, side-lining important but less lucrative claims. Problems may occur if funders have relationships with lawyers or are competitors of the defendant.⁴⁵ Funders are often professional organizations that rely on the success of claims to sustain their business models, which motivates them to generally support meritorious and well-founded legal claims. This professional assessment can contribute to a more disciplined approach to litigation, potentially reducing frivolous lawsuits.⁴⁶ Some believe litigation finance can serve as a signal to courts and defendants, indicating the merit or lack thereof in legal claims.⁴⁷ Further safeguards can be provided by specific disclosure orders, and by ensuring that attorneys adhere to their ethical duties to maintain their independence.⁴⁸

One recent case from the USA underscores the potential need differentiated levels of protection from funders interference with the merits of the process, depending on the profile of the funded party – sophisticated or not. In early 2023, Sysco, a major food distributor, and Burford, a leading litigation finance firm, initiated legal actions against each other in Illinois and New York. The conflict arose after Burford secured an injunction through arbitration, which barred Sysco from settling an antitrust claim without Burford's agreement. Sysco argued that the injunction, based on a clause in their funding agreement, was against public policy and should be annulled. Conversely, Burford maintained that as a sophisticated party, Sysco was

⁴³ Cordina A., *op.cit.*, p. 275.

⁴⁴ Cordina A., *op.cit.*, p. 275.

⁴⁵ Such was the notable Gawker Media case. <https://content.next.westlaw.com/practical-law/document/lcdcf2f8a29b711e698dc8b09b4f043e0/Hulk-Hogan-Wrestles-Gawker-With-Third-Party-Litigation-Financing?viewType=FullText&transitionType=Default&contextData={sc.Default}>

⁴⁶ Marquais, O., Grec, A., *Do's and Dont's of Regulating Third-Party Litigation Funding: Singapore vs. France*, Asian International Arbitration Journal, 16 (1), SIAC, Wolters Kluwer, 2020, pp. 49-68, p. 53.

⁴⁷ Avraham, R., Wickelgren, A., *Third-Party Litigation Funding — A Signaling Model*, 63 DEPAUL LAW REV 2014, p. 256.

⁴⁸ Wendel, W. B. (2019), p. 48.

entitled to transfer settlement rights, and the injunction was essential to protect their contractual rights. Ultimately, Sysco and Burford settled privately, with Sysco assigning all its claim rights to Burford, eliminating any chance of Sysco settling the claims independently. This resolution left the enforceability of Burford's arbitral award untested in New York courts but supported the arbitrators' decision validating the injunction and Sysco's right to assign settlement rights.⁴⁹

The views of legal theorists on TPF cover a broad spectrum of opinions, ranging from those who hail it as "likely the most important development in civil justice of our time"⁵⁰ to those who are sceptical and assume that litigation finance will encourage frivolous litigation and allow profit-seeking investors to dominate our civil justice system.⁵¹ Scholarly and professional reviews are dominantly forward-looking; they primarily focus on the effects of litigation finance after a legal claim has been made and a party seeks funding. However, the impact of TPF on parties' behaviours *before* and *after* litigation cannot be overlooked.⁵² Some authors argue that TPF serves as an enforcement mechanism, enhancing the likelihood that parties can effectively enforce their legal rights, thus influencing pre-litigation behaviour by reducing the probability that e.g. a contracting party will breach the agreement.⁵³ It aids liquidity - or risk-constrained litigants in initiating legal actions and supports them in securing better legal representation, developing stronger litigation strategies, and resisting financial pressures to settle for less than the full value of their claim.⁵⁴ Revealing both the existence of litigation funding and the identity of the funder - but not the entire content of Litigation Finance Agreement (LFA) - to the opposing side during the litigation can serve as a strategic advantage. If the funder is known for meticulously evaluating and investing in cases with a high likelihood of success, this disclosure may signal the strength of the case to the opposing party.

⁴⁹ For broader comment, see: Baker, T., *What Litigation Funders Can Learn About Settlement Rights From the Law of Liability Insurance*, Institute for Law and Economics, University of Pennsylvania Carey Law School, Research Paper n. 23-41, [Electronic version], 2023, Retrieved April 11, 2024, from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4638617>

⁵⁰ Steinitz, M., *Follow the Money? A Proposed Approach for Disclosure of Litigation Finance Agreements*, 53 U.C. DAVIS L. REV. 1073, 1075, 2019.

⁵¹ Kidd, J., *To Fund or Not to Fund: The Need for Second-Best Solutions to the Litigation Finance Dilemma*, 8 J.L. ECON. & POL'Y 613, 627-29, 2012; Rubin, P. H., *Third-Party Financing of Litigation*, 38 N. KY. L. REV. 673, 675, 2011.

⁵² Bedi, S., Marra, W. C., *The Shadows of Litigation Finance*, 74 Vanderbilt Law Review 563, 2021, p. 570.

⁵³ *Ibid.*, pp. 591-602.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

The balance of enabling access to justice through TPF while preventing potential conflicts of interest and ensuring fair outcomes for all parties involved remains a critical issue in the ongoing evolution of litigation funding, but given the multifaceted complexity of TPF, a “one-size fits all” approach could be inappropriate.⁵⁵ Certain concerns are largely unfounded, and those that are valid can be addressed through an appropriate regulatory framework, where transparency in the process is crucial for assessing the funder capital adequacy, funders’ share in awarded sums, business models of funders, and determination of the absence of conflict of interest.

2.3. Charting the Course for a Sustainable Third-Party Funding

At the moment TPF is mostly unregulated, although the TPF landscape has witnessed significant evolution in the recent years. It’s evident that the lack of regulation does not meet the challenges posed by the rapid development of this practices, despite the fact that the operation of TPLF as a distinct business model contributes to its robust self-regulation.⁵⁶

In Europe, the TPF industry is most developed in England and Wales, the Netherlands, and Germany,⁵⁷ although the degree of acceptance varies within the judiciary.⁵⁸ In jurisdictions like the UK, where TPF has a longer history, there has been a shift from initial self-regulation, characterized by voluntary codes created by associations of third-party funders,⁵⁹ to the development of more formal codes of conduct for litigation funders.⁶⁰

TPF found a welcoming environment in international and domestic arbitration, favoured for its alignment with party autonomy and the commercial interests of private entities.⁶¹ Several arbitral institutions, such as

⁵⁵ Kramer, X., in Cordina, A., Storskrubb, E., *The Future of Regulation of Third-Party Litigation Funding in Europe*, Conference Report, 2022, Erasmus University Rotterdam.

⁵⁶ Marquis, O., Grec, A., *op.cit.*, p. 59. For an economic analysis of law regarding the TPF, see: Cordina, A., *Is It All That Fishy? A Critical Review of the Concerns Surrounding Third Party Litigation Funding in Europe*, Erasmus Law Review, 2021, no. 4, pp. 270-280.

⁵⁷ Stadler, A., *Third Party Funding of Mass Litigation in Germany: Entrepreneurial Parties – Curse or Blessing?*, Privatizing Dispute Resolution (eds. L. Cadiet, B. Hess & M.R. Isidro), 2019, pp. 209-231, p. 209. Also, Lohmann, U. et al, *Litigation Funding 2024 (Germany): Trends and Developments*, 2024, <https://practiceguides.chambers.com/practice-guides/litigation-funding-2024/germany/trends-and-developments/016152>

⁵⁸ Cordina, A., *op.cit.*, p. 271.

⁵⁹ Jackson, R., “Review of Civil Litigation Costs: Final Report”, p. 119.

⁶⁰ For example, see. Code of Conduct for Litigation Funders for England and Wales, available at <https://associationoflitigationfunders.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Code-Of-Conduct-for-Litigation-Funders-at-Jan-2018-FINAL.pdf>

⁶¹ Chatterjee, P., Singhanian, A., Gel B., *Third-Party Funding: Treading on Thin Ice*, [Electronic

ICSID in 2022⁶² and ICC in 2021,⁶³ have incorporated rules addressing TPF with a focus on disclosure requirements concerning the involvement and identity of funders.

In contrast, the European Parliament proposed a much stricter regulatory framework in its Resolution 2022.⁶⁴ Originating from ideas by German MEP Axel Voss,⁶⁵ the resolution suggests a European Directive to regulate third-party litigation funding. The Recommended Directive Proposal on responsible financing does not mandate the acceptance of the third-party funding (TPF) mechanism for Member States, but if they choose to do so, the directive proposal demands adherence to the specified minimum standards.⁶⁶ Where third-party funding activities are permitted, Member States are required to establish a system for the authorization and monitoring of litigation funders' activities within their territory. The *Recommended proposal of a directive* includes creating an authorization system for funders with capital requirements, setting up supervisory authorities, introducing a fiduciary duty towards clients, mandating specific terms for funding agreements, prohibiting influence on dispute management, capping funder profits at 40% of the award, preventing funders from limiting liability for adverse costs, and requiring the disclosure of complete funding agreements under certain conditions.⁶⁷

The European Parliament report portrays a largely negative stance on TPLF, emphasizing its perceived drawbacks and potential for misuse rather

version], 2023, Retrieved February 27, 2024, from <https://arbitrationblog.kluwerarbitration.com/2023/08/27/third-party-funding-treading-on-thin-ice/>

⁶² https://icsid.worldbank.org/sites/default/files/documents/ICSID_Convention.pdf

⁶³ <https://iccwbo.org/news-publications/news/icc-court-releases-updates-to-its-note-ahead-of-2021-icc-arbitration-rules/>

⁶⁴ European Parliament resolution of 13 September 2022 with recommendations to the Commission on Responsible private funding of litigation (2020/2130(INL)). https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2022-0308_EN.pdf

⁶⁵ REPORT with recommendations to the Commission on Responsible private funding of litigation, 25.7.2022 - (2020/2130(INL)). https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2022-0218_EN.html

⁶⁶ Recital 3 and 7 of the Proposal. This is evident from Article 4 of the Recommended proposal, which states that Member States may decide, in accordance with their national laws, whether to permit third-party funding agreements in connection with proceedings within their jurisdiction, for the benefit of claimants or intended beneficiaries residing within their territory.

⁶⁷ For detailed analysis pro et contra on disclosure obligations, see: Mandatory Disclosure Rules for Dispute Financing, Center on Civil Justice, New York University School of Law. <https://www.law.nyu.edu/sites/default/files/CCJ%20Mandatory%20Disclosure%20Book.pdf>

than its promotion.⁶⁸ This is not the EU's first regulatory attempt at TPLF - the Collective Redress Directive⁶⁹ allows member states to enable private TPF though without a clear stance on how much consumers should be able to lose from their compensation if the lawsuit succeeds.⁷⁰ TPLF in Europe, still developing, has shown no major abuses, suggesting that a proportional regulatory framework is more suitable than a complete ban.⁷¹ Such frameworks should balance the need to prevent misuse without unduly hindering legitimate business models of funders or limiting access to justice. Given the dominantly procedural nature of rules on TPF, in the absence of harmonised procedural rules in the EU, many aspects of litigation costs regulation will still be regulated at the domestic level and the potential EU approach would likely be a piecemeal one.⁷²

3. Controlling and Enforcing Litigation Funding Agreements in Cross-Border Context

Litigation funding represents a significant and modern development, transcending national boundaries to operate within an international framework.⁷³ Considering TPF in cross-border litigation raises several issues. Firstly, the fundamental dilemma is whether TPF, as a concept based on a LFA, is predominantly procedural or substantive in nature. The relationship between the funder and the funded party in the process appears as a contract of a predominantly substantive legal nature, which involves the provision of services. It seems evident that the rules governing the permissibility of financing litigation costs through third-party funds are of procedural nature, highlighting their application as procedural *lex fori*. The permissibility and conditions under which TPLF is allowed—in terms of obligations towards

⁶⁸ Meller-Hannich, C., Gsell, B., *Die Regulierung privater Prozessfinanzierung in der EU Entschließung und EU-Richtlinienvorschlag: Legitime Ziele, überschießende Umsetzung?*, pp. 160-164. [Electronic version], 2023, Retrieved February 28, 2024, from <https://anwaltsblatt.anwaltverein.de/files/anwaltsblatt.de/anwaltsblatt-online/2023-160.pdf>

⁶⁹ Directive (EU) 2020/1828 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2020 on representative actions for the protection of the collective interests of consumers and repealing Directive 2009/22/EC (Text with EEA relevance). https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2020.409.01.0001.01.ENG

⁷⁰ Art. 10 in connection to the art. 12 (2) of the Collective Redress Directive (EU) 2020/1828n.

⁷¹ Meller-Hannich C., Gsell, B., op.cit., pp. 160-164.

⁷² Professor Van Calster in Cordina A. And Storskrubb E., *The Future of Regulation of Third-Party Litigation Funding in Europe*, Conference Report, 2022, Erasmus University Rotterdam.

⁷³ Hodges, C., Peysner, J., Nurse, A., *Litigation Fundings: Status and Issues*, Research Report, Centre for Socio-Legal Studies, Oxford and University of Lincoln Law School, 2012, p. 38.

the court and the opposing party, disclosure requirements, transparency, conflicts of interest, fiduciary duty, prohibition of influence on parties, and responsibility for adverse costs—are typically regulated by procedural law, which in turn impacts the content of litigation financing contracts and consequently, the substantive legal relationships between the financier and the funded party. Such approach is visible for arbitration rules and those rules which regulate TPF.⁷⁴ Power of the court or arbitral tribunal to order disclosure of the funding agreement seems crucial for the exercise of any form of control over procedural effect of third party funding arrangement.

The issue of confidentiality, especially in arbitral proceedings, necessitates careful consideration. Funders are typically not subjected to the same professional ethical rules as lawyers concerning the handling of confidential information and conflicts of interest. Consequently, concerns have been voiced⁷⁵ about the absence of legislative or professional restrictions preventing TPF from utilizing information from one party in a separate funded case for a different party.

Maintaining ethical standards in third-party legal funding is complex, especially in relation to attorney-client privilege and lawyer independence. Legal privilege ensures client confidentiality, prohibiting attorneys from sharing protected information with third parties like funders without clear consent from the client. This confidentiality is essential for maintaining the integrity of the legal process and safeguarding client interests from external pressures.⁷⁶ Additionally, the independence of lawyers is crucial in preventing undue influence from funders who have a financial interest in the case. Such funders might push for premature settlements or discontinuation of the case under unfavourable terms. Lawyers must act in their clients' best interests, avoid advising funders, take instructions solely from their clients, and avoid meeting funders without the client being present.⁷⁷ This situation presents a tension between the transparency needed by funders to evaluate a case and the lawyers' ethical necessity to protect client interests. In some jurisdictions, such as Turkey, Portugal, and Sweden, information held by a funder, unlike that held by a lawyer, is not protected by professional secre-

⁷⁴ E.g. ICC Arbitration Rules and VIAC Rules introduce a requirement of party disclosure of third-party funding arrangements. Lazić, M., Savić M., *Third Party Funding and Access to Justice*, Revija Kopaoničke škole prirodnog prava, 2/2021, p. 137.

⁷⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 141.

⁷⁶ Marquais O. and Grec A., "Do's and Dont's of Regulating Third-Party Litigation Funding: Singapore vs. France", *Asian International Arbitration Journal*, Vol. 16 (1), SIAC, Wolters Kluwer, 2020, 49-68, p. 65-66.

⁷⁷ *Ibid.*

cy.⁷⁸ Consequently, a funder might be required, for example, by a court order, to disclose this information. Additionally, sharing information with a funder could be interpreted as waiving the secrecy typically granted, making the information potentially admissible as evidence. This risk can be mitigated by drafting a carefully worded confidentiality agreement.⁷⁹ Some civil law jurisdictions are exploring ways to extend privilege protections to include funders. Another approach to ensuring secrecy is for the funder to hire its own lawyers to review the case, thereby benefiting from the lawyers' professional secrecy protections.⁸⁰

It seems that one of the crucial questions is how much autonomy do parties in funding agreement enjoy. Litigation investment is a complex form of economic activity that does not neatly fit into traditional categories such as commercial lending, insurance, joint ventures, venture capital, or alternative lawyer-client fee arrangements. It is better understood as a relational contract—a long-term commercial relationship where the parties' rights and obligations evolve over time and may be adjusted based on changing circumstances.⁸¹ This approach recognizes litigation investment as involving shared ownership of a cause of action, viewed as an asset whose value can fluctuate based on the behaviour of the involved parties.⁸² Civil law countries in Europe have taken a relatively *laissez-faire* stance towards this funding method, lacking specific legislation and having limited case law, thereby allowing industry stakeholders to define the regulatory framework. LFAs are typically confidential and seldom exposed to professional scrutiny,⁸³ which significantly complicates detailed analysis of TPF practices.

LFAs are increasingly recognized as *sui generis* contracts, which means they are unique and do not fit neatly into traditional contract categories. As such, general principles of contract law are applicable to LFAs. This flexibility does not necessarily guarantee adequate protection for claimants, who are often legal entities and thus outside the scope of consumer protection laws designed for natural persons.

⁷⁸ The ICCA Report, p. 137.

⁷⁹ This seems as an effective protection for secret information in Netherlands, Russia, Germany and Japan. The ICCA Report, fn 321 p. 137.

⁸⁰ *Ibid.*

⁸¹ Sebok, A. J., Wendel, W. B., *Duty in the Litigation-Investment Agreement: The Choice between Tort and Contract Norms when the Deal Breaks Down*, (2013). Cornell Law Faculty Publications, p. 670.

⁸² *Ibid.*

⁸³ Steinitz, M., Field, A., *A Model Litigation Finance Contract*, Scholarly Commons at Boston University School of Law, Boston University School of Law, 2014, pp. 711-771.

Along with classifying the contract as *sui generis*,⁸⁴ there are also suggestions to consider LFAs as composite contracts.⁸⁵ In some jurisdictions, qualification of the LFAs depends on the type of the funded case, e.g. in collective action cases the funder will usually have a much more active role in managing and steering the litigation. The agreements between the funder and the individual clients will then generally be structured as a contract for services rather than a mere funding agreement, including provisions that enable the funder to manage the litigation.⁸⁶

The multifaceted nature of TPF was highlighted in the case before the UK Supreme Court⁸⁷, in which the Court challenged the legality of LFAs, holding that LFAs that allow funders to recover a percentage of damages are, in fact, damages-based agreements (DBAs) and enforceable only if they comply with the detailed legal regime for DBAs. This ruling, which overturned previous decisions by lower courts, casts doubt on the future of TPF, indicating a need for a thorough review of existing LFAs in light of this significant judgment. Until this moment, DBAs had generally been seen as agreements that only lawyers or other advisers – and not funders – would (or even could) enter into with claimants.⁸⁸ However, since then, draft legislation has been introduced to carve out opt-out collective proceedings from the effect of the judgment, the Competition Appeal Tribunal has approved funding agreements that provide for the funder’s remuneration to be calculated as a multiple of the funds provided or a percentage of any damages to the extent enforceable and permitted by law, and the Ministry of Justice announced that the Lord Chancellor will introduce legislation to restore the litigation funding position that existed before PACCAR.⁸⁹

⁸⁴ The parties’ respective rights and obligations can be freely defined in the funding agreement, the sole limitation being violations of public policy. Given the lack of a statutory framework or specific legislation, the funding agreement should be comprehensive and should stipulate all aspects of the parties’ relationship. Fremault, E., *Spotlights: structuring litigation funding agreement in Luxembourg*, *Deminor Litigation Funding*, [Electronic version], 2022, Retrieved March 4, 2024, from <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=9dc78bcb-0e06-41f8-84d0-08de7f05e635>

⁸⁵ Marquais, O., Grec, A., *op.cit.*, p. 65.

⁸⁶ For Belgium, see: *Spotlight: structuring litigation funding agreements in Belgium*, *Deminor Litigation Funding*, [Electronic version], 2022, Retrieved March 4, 2024, from <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=2975ff09-9b04-414a-ace4-9a8117677fa4>

⁸⁷ *R (on the application of PACCAR Inc. and Others) v. Competition Appeal Tribunal and Others*. <https://www.supremecourt.uk/cases/uksc-2021-0078.html>

⁸⁸ Supreme Court deals blow to litigation funders in CAT, Slaughter and May, 2023. Available at <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=c1646ad0-7426-4c35-9ef3-4ceb9547c4c6>

⁸⁹ *Litigation Funding Agreements: Developments Since PACCAR*, Cooley LLP, 2024. Available

The feasibility and enforceability of LFAs may be problematic if these agreements are considered contrary to public policy or illegal. The contractual autonomy in LFAs is restricted by mandatory rules that are typically contained in the procedural law of the jurisdiction where the case involving the litigation funder is being processed.

Just as the concept, nature, rights, and obligations arising from LFAs are not precisely defined, the status of litigation funders is also not clearly regulated. Are they financial services providers or legal services providers?⁹⁰ If they are perceived as the latter, they can first and foremost be considered as having duties to their client and to the court.⁹¹ Litigation funders represent a new category of financial players that currently fall outside traditional financial service regulations. Given their growing influence in the justice system, it might be appropriate to view them as 'systemically important' to the judicial process, warranting specific regulatory oversight of their corporate governance. However, self-regulation has shown limited effectiveness in ensuring compliance and ethical behaviour.⁹² This suggests a need for more robust, enforceable regulations to govern the activities of litigation funders to safeguard the integrity of the justice system.⁹³

4. Conclusion

TPF is a swiftly expanding and largely unregulated practice that leaves no one indifferent, reflecting its wide array of potential benefits and concerns. As TPF continues to evolve globally, it is evident that the uncertainties and challenges inherent in its contractual frameworks must be systematically addressed through legislative amendments and judicial precedents. If these issues remain unresolved, TPF may only serve a limited and unpredictable role in the justice delivery system.

at <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=6f7041a6-1104-496e-8ed7-2ae46f01ad34>

⁹⁰ Professor Van Calster in Cordina A. And Storskrubb E., „The Future of Regulation of Third-Party Litigation Funding in Europe“, Conference Report, 2022, Erasmus University Rotterdam.

⁹¹ *Ibid.*

⁹² For example, in the United Kingdom, only a quarter of the funders belong to the Association of Litigation Funders, which enforces a self-regulatory code. The penalties under this code, such as a 500 GBP fine or expulsion from the association, are relatively mild and do not effectively deter misconduct. Uncharted Waters. An Analysis of Third-Party Litigation Funding in European Collective Redress; US Chamber Institute for Legal Reform, October 2019. Available at https://www.pf.uni-lj.si/media/analysis_of_tplf_funding_in_the_european_collective_redress.pdf

⁹³ https://www.amchameu.eu/system/files/position_papers/tplf_final.pdf

The necessity for flexible regulation is clear. Policymakers and legislators are urged to establish a specific regulatory framework for TPF, grounded in a comprehensive analysis of its pros and cons, supported by robust legal theory research. This regulatory framework should initially take a principled stance on the permissibility of TPF. The enforceability of Litigation Funding Agreements can be contentious, particularly if these agreements are deemed contrary to public policy or illegal. Given that the contractual autonomy in LFAs is often circumscribed by mandatory rules in procedural law, ignoring these complexities is not feasible. For the sake of legal certainty, predictability in legal relationships, and enhancing transparent access to justice, it is imperative to strike a balance. This balance must not stifle TPF where it can genuinely improve access to justice and level the playing field for parties with significant economic disparities.

Furthermore, resolving potential conflicts between funders and funded parties warrants attention. Given the expected professionalism of funders, it is likely that Litigation Funding Agreements will include a clause for choosing the governing law. Given that such contracts are often classified as *sui generis*, where general contract law rules apply, the determination of governing law for an LFA with a cross-border element, in the absence of a chosen law, would typically invoke conflict of laws rules, with the funder's characteristic performance as the relevant criterion, thereby applying the law of the funder's domicile. This approach underscores the importance of a nuanced and well-informed regulatory strategy to govern this complex field.

Summary

Third-Party Funding is rapidly expanding and largely unregulated, significantly impacting the legal landscape with its potential benefits and challenges. As TPF evolves globally, the need for a clear regulatory framework becomes apparent, especially to address the uncertainties in its contractual frameworks through legislative changes and judicial precedents. Without proper regulation, TPF might only serve a limited and unpredictable role in justice systems. A flexible regulatory approach is crucial. Policymakers and legislators are urged to create specific regulations for TPF, grounded in thorough analysis of its advantages and disadvantages. These regulations should clarify where TPF is permissible, ensuring legal certainty and transparent access to justice. This is vital, as the enforceability of Litigation Funding Agreements (LFAs) can be contentious, especially if these agreements conflict with public policy or legal norms. TPF is likely to remain a permanent fixture in the legal system, and ignoring it will not mitigate potential

negative effects such as disproportionate profits for funders, vulnerability of funded parties, and the risk of contract terminations. Issues such as the fundamental permissibility of TPF, conditions for its use, and court oversight fall within procedural law and are vital for maintaining fair legal processes. Moreover, addressing potential conflicts between funders and funded parties is essential. This emphasizes the importance of a well-informed regulatory strategy that can adapt to the complexities of TPF and ensure it continues to facilitate access to justice without compromising the fairness of the legal system.

Keywords: *Third-Party Funding (TPF), Litigation Funding Agreements (LFAs), cross border litigation, access to justice.*

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